

Study of geometrical effects on slosh induced damping

Marco Pizzoli*, Francesco Saltari†, Giuliano Coppotelli‡, Franco Mastroddi§
Dept. of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering
Sapienza University of Rome
Via Eudossiana 18, 00184 Rome, Italy
franco.mastroddi@uniroma1.it

The effort to reduce the costs and environmental impact of modern commercial aircraft requires an ever-better understanding of aircraft physics, including the characterization of the effective damping introduced on a structure by slosh dynamics. Recent studies have been aimed at identifying reduced-order models for scaled sloshing that require simplifying assumptions and scaling processes. These models need further experimental verification to be integrated within full-scale structural and aeroelastic frameworks. In this framework, the purpose of this paper is to experimentally investigate the combined effects of rotation and vertical tank motion on the dissipative behaviour of sloshing. Specifically, a controlled electrodynamic shaker is used to provide vertical displacement to a rigid hinged beam on which is mounted a box-shaped tank partially filled with water. The experimental setup allows the tank to be positioned at various points on the beam so that the energy dissipated by the sloshing fluid can be evaluated under different scenarios of combined tank motion.

I. Introduction

THE dissipating effects of a fluid inside commercial aircraft tanks have not specifically been looked at in the past to reduce the resulting dynamic loads. The identification and the study of such dynamic effects can make it possible to design less conservative aircraft configurations in the future, thus enabling increasingly lighter structures and, as a consequence, having a less polluting impact on the environment. Aeronautical structures usually withstand loads occurring from gusts, turbulence and landing impacts. The sloshing of fuel generally stowed in the wings caused by vertical accelerations is coupled with the structural dynamics of the aircraft by means of impacts between fluid propellant and tank walls. This type of sloshing is well known to provide a noticeable increase in the overall structural damping. The development of models and the experimental characterization of such a phenomena is framed in the European project H2020 SLOshing Wing Dynamics (SLOWD) aiming with an heuristic approach (combining experimental and numerical data) at characterising sloshing dynamics for its use in future aircraft design (Ref. [1]). Vertical slosh dynamics is one of the possible dynamics of the fluid stowed in the tanks which, when it occurs, exhibits different characteristics compared to the classic sloshing, generally occurring with rotations and lateral motions of the tank (see Refs. [2–5]). The latter motion generates standing waves inside the cavity providing dynamic coupling with structure and possible modification of the aero-mechanic properties of the flying system such as flutter margins. Specifically, the effects of sloshing on aircraft aeroelastic flutter stability was considered in Refs. [6–8]. On the other hand, the sloshing induced by the vertical acceleration of the tank, hence perpendicular to the free surface, still needs investigation. At very low excitation levels, the free surface tends to remain flat. By increasing the level of vertical acceleration some modes can become unstable depending on the oscillation frequency (Refs. [3, 9–11]). These nonlinearities will generate fluid fingers that can reach the tank ceiling. By increasing the level of acceleration even more, the transition to a completely chaotic regime takes place. Indeed, higher values of vertical acceleration trigger Rayleigh-Taylor instabilities (Ref. [12]), determining a chaotic flow regime with air/water mixing. At this level of excitation, coherent structures related to the sloshing modes are no longer recognised owe to free surface fragmentation. The energy dissipation occurs due to the phase shift between the sloshing forces when the fluid impacts on the tank roof and the movement imposed on the tank, and its amount is interpreted to be mainly linked to the intensity of the impacts (Ref. [13–15]). More in details, filling level and surface tension seem to play a key role to this behaviour, since affect the relative acceleration of the floating fluid droplets can reach with respect to the tank walls, thus exchanging momentum with the container.

*PhD student.

†Research fellow.

‡Associate Professor.

§Full Professor.

Previous experimental fluid-structure interaction campaigns in which a tank system was positioned at the tip of a beam, representing a wing, showed how this type of chaotic response induces a very damped response of the structure (Refs. [13–17]). The total balancing of elastic potential energy and fluid energy results in a noticeable increase in the effective damping of the structural motion.

Reference [18] provides an experimental characterisation of the nonlinear dissipative behaviour of the sloshing fluid inside a tank placed in purely vertical motion. The energy dissipated by the fluid was quantified for different values of the oscillation amplitudes and frequencies. These two parameters are related to the ideal unsteady harmonic boundary conditions that a vertically vibrating structure can impose to the walls of a tank (which triggers the slosh dynamics). A proper metric for the definition of dissipating energy was introduced thus mapping the damping introduced by the sloshing dynamics corresponding to different filling levels. The proposed metric was inspired by works like the one presented in Ref. [19] where suitable energy maps were used for prediction and control strategies applied to aeroelastic airfoil response to gusts.

This experimental campaign enabled the identification of data-driven reduced-order models for sloshing that, for their use within full-scale frameworks, require appropriate scaling operations (see Refs. [20, 21]). Among the assumptions underlying the employed scaling process is the one that local tank rotations due to wing bending are negligible as well as centrifugal effects due to shortening (which although irrelevant at the level of structural dynamics for small perturbations, can generate effects on a fluid stowed on the tank Ref. [22]). The aim of this paper is to conduct a sensitivity analysis with respect to the degrees of freedom of the tank to be considered in the sloshing ROM synthesis, to validate the goodness of the hypothesis in which the tank is assumed to move merely in vertical direction. Indeed, so far, it is well accepted that rotations and centrifugal forces due to the bending-induced shortening have a role in speeding up the transient to a complete chaotic regime (a pure vertical motion requires more time to develop fingers reaching the tank ceiling) but their effects in changing the fluid dynamics scenario thus impacting on the level of dissipation that can be introduced in the tank in steady harmonic regime is not yet investigated. To this end, a new experimental set-up is designed to ensure simultaneous vertical and rotational excitation of the tank using the same shaker (and box-shaped tank) as in Ref. [18]. Specifically, the set-up allows the tank to be mounted on a rigid hinged beam set into rotation by the vertical vibrations imposed by the shaker extender to which it is connected (via a hinge). The study is carried out by quantifying the energy dissipated by sloshing as the degree of combination between vertical and rotational motion of the tank varies. The degree of combination is varied by placing the tank in different positions on the beam, emphasizing more or less the rotational contribution than the vertical one. In this paper, two different tank positions on the rotating beam are considered, resulting in two case studies. Comparison with purely vertical sloshing-induced dissipation reveals how the tank rotation in the two aforementioned cases influences the total energy balance. Furthermore, the same type of sensitivity analysis is repeated to assess the influence of tank rotations on the sloshing-effective mass fraction, already introduced in Ref. [21]. It should be noted that, the experimental data required for the above study are gathered, using the appropriate sensors, by performing harmonic excitation tests at varying frequency and amplitude.

The three experimental case studies and their components description are presented in Sec. II, while Sec. III presents the comparison of results, preceded by the introduction of a dimensional analysis of the energy dissipated by sloshing and its calculation procedure. Finally, a section of concluding remarks ends the paper.

II. Experimental case studies and set-up

The experimental test-bed of the present analysis realizes a sloshing problem with a box-shaped tank having a height of $h = 27.2$ mm and base of sides $l_1 = 117.2$ mm and $l_2 = 78$ mm (See Fig. 1(a)). These dimensions are chosen in order to trigger slamming with the tank roof after Rayleigh-Taylor instabilities. The tank is the same employed in Ref. [18] to characterize the dissipation caused by sloshing when the tank is set in a purely vertical harmonic motion.

Two experimental set-up are considered in this work. In the first one, the tank is placed directly on an electrodynamic shaker (see Fig. 1(b)) capable of imposing vertical vibrations with a minimum frequency of 5 Hz and amplitude of 25 mm peak-to-peak. The quantification of the energy dissipated by the fluid is performed in accordance with Ref. [18] for different values of the amplitude and frequency of the imposed vertical harmonic motion. These last two parameters are strictly related to the unsteady boundary conditions that a vertically vibrating structure can impose to an interfacing tank. The operative ranges considered covered both the region of small perturbation where Faraday waves occur, and the region characterized by the presence intense impacts between liquid and tank ceiling caused by high accelerations following the fragmentation of the free surface due to the Rayleigh-Taylor instability. The dynamic load at the interface between shaker and tank is measured by two load cells (See Fig. 1(a)), symmetrically placed along the mid-line of the long side of the tank base. The overall force exchanged by tank and shaker f_S is the sum of the two load cells.

Fig. 1 Experimental set-up for purely vertical sloshing dissipated energy characterization

Additionally, the system is equipped with two redundant accelerometers mounted on the upper closure side of the tank, and an accelerometer used by the shaker controller.

In the second experimental set-up, the introduced tank (see Fig. 1(a)) is mounted on a rigid beam with a length of $L_1 = 600$ mm hinged at two points (See Fig. 2). The innermost hinge is fixed and only allows rotation of the beam. The second one connects with a linear guide the beam to the extender (*i.e.*, a rigid beam having length $L_2 = 600$ mm) of the electrodynamic shaker (same used in the first configuration and in Ref. [18]). As a result of the excitation imposed by the shaker, this hinge moves vertically (and slightly laterally, through the linear guide) allowing a rigid rotation of the beam with the tank on it (See Fig. 2(b)). This makes it possible to assign a combined vertical-rotational motion to the tank. From a geometrical point of view, the parameter $\phi = l_1/l$ is introduced in order to distinguish different case studies based on the distance l between the tank geometric centre and the fixed hinge. Note that, the first experimental set-up (see Fig. 1(b)) is considered as a limit case in which the distance l tends to infinity. The dynamic load at the interface between the beam and the tank is measured again by the two load cells shown in Fig. 1(a), placed along the mid-line of the long side of the tank base. The overall force exchanged by tank and the rigid beam is the sum of the two load cells. Due to the rotation of the tank θ , the sloshing liquid also exerts a moment m_S (whose origin is assumed to coincide with the geometric centre of the tank), which can be obtained experimentally by multiplying the distance separating the load cells by the difference between the measured forces. The system is also equipped with two accelerometers placed on the rotating beam, one underneath the geometric centre of the tank and the other halfway between the latter and the fixed hinge. A redundant accelerometer is installed directly on the shaker to monitor the imposed vibrations. This experimental system also acts as an amplifier of the motion that a shaker can supply directly to a tank if it were mounted on to it (as shown in Fig. 1(b)). Based on the distance l from the fixed hinge point and the rigidity of the beam, the tank rotation θ is obtained through geometric considerations by integrating accelerometer measurements.

III. Quantification of the dissipated energy and sloshing-effective mass fraction

The experimental configurations presented in the previous section are used to conduct a sensitivity analysis of the dissipative sloshing behaviour with respect to the degree of combination between vertical and rotational tank motion. Three case studies are discussed and compared. In the first, the tank experiences only vertical motion by employing the first experimental set-up (see Fig. 1). Therefore the rotation of the tank is zero ($\phi = 0$). On the other hand, the other two case studies consist of the tank mounted, respectively, at the tip of the L_1 rotating rigid beam ($\phi = 0.26$) and halfway between the fixed hinge and the beam tip ($\phi = 0.52$). Harmonic tests with variable frequency and amplitude (VFA) are performed, in the case of tank half filled with water, in order to get the force measurements for energy computation by setting an acquisition time of 480 s.

For instance, Fig. 3(a) shows, for the $\phi = 0$ case, the force data used for the dissipation evaluation, measured at the acceleration and excitation frequency equal to $3g$ and $17Hz$ respectively. Specifically, Fig. 3(a) shows the trend over time of the sloshing force f_S , normalized by the purely inertial contribution ($m_l a \Omega^2$), where m_l is the mass of the liquid, while a and Ω are the oscillation amplitude and frequency of the vertical imposed motion $w(t) = a \cos(\Omega t)$.

(a) Experimental configuration

(b) Experimental configuration schematic

Fig. 2 Experimental set-up for vertically-rotating sloshing tank problem

Note that the oscillation amplitude is linked to the acceleration amplitude through the excitation frequency. Figure 3(b) shows the hysteresis cycles obtained by plotting the variation of the normalized sloshing force with respect to the normalized vertical harmonic displacement imposed by the tank $w(t)/a$. Being the rotation of the tank null in this case, the area enclosed by the hysteresis cycles represents the work L_d done by the sloshing force f_S in a vertical harmonic motion cycle at the specific amplitude-frequency pair (see Ref. [18]). This work corresponds precisely to the energy dissipated by sloshing dynamics.

More in general, the dissipated work is also affected by the rotation of the tank θ and is consequently expressed as follows:

$$L_d(\Omega, a) = \oint_{cycle} f_S(\Omega, a) dw + \oint_{cycle} m_S(\Omega, a) d\theta \quad (1)$$

$$= \int_0^{2\pi/\Omega} \left(f_S(\Omega, a) \dot{w} + m_S(\Omega, a) \dot{\theta} \right) dt \quad (2)$$

where the additional contribution associated with the sloshing moment m_S is introduced. The dimensional analysis (carried out using the π -theorem) in Eq. 3 highlights the most important non-dimensional parameters on which the dissipated energy L_d depends, being $\Phi_d = L_d/(m_l a^2 \Omega^2)$ the non-dimensional dissipated energy.

$$L_d = m_l a^2 \Omega^2 \Phi_d(\bar{\omega}, \bar{a}, \phi, \alpha, \lambda_1, \lambda_2, Re, Bo, \dots) \quad (3)$$

Besides the non-dimensional excitation frequency $\bar{\omega} = \Omega/\sqrt{g/h}$ and vertical displacement amplitude $\bar{a} = a/h$, L_d is dependent on the filling level α , the Reynolds number $Re = \nu h/\nu$ (ν kinematic viscosity) that reflects viscosity effects, and the Bond number $Bo = \rho g h^2/\gamma$ (γ surface tension) that reflects surface tension effects. Furthermore, the dissipated energy may also depend on the aspect ratios relative to the dimensions in the tank plane, referred to as $\lambda_1 = h/l_1$ and $\lambda_2 = h/l_2$, respectively. For purely vertical sloshing dynamics, the most important dimensionless parameters are the frequency $\bar{\omega}$ and the ratio between the amplitude of motion and the height of the tank \bar{a} . Capillarity may have an influence on dissipation, but numerical studies have shown that parameters more related to the physical properties of the fluid (Reynolds and Bond) provide a negligible contribution on the dissipative capabilities during violent vertical sloshing phenomena (Ref. [23]). The liquid impacts with the tank roof that occur during these phenomena influence the

Fig. 3 Sloshing force and hysteresis cycle for the point (3g, 17Hz) of the purely vertical excitation ($\phi = 0$)

dissipation, erasing memory effects of the sloshing dynamics at high oscillation amplitudes. Accordingly, the tank height h plays the key role since the ullage drives the amount of kinetic energy stored by the liquid that is dissipated during the impacts (Ref. [24]). The aspect ratios of the tank are much less important compared to the tank height (Refs. [18, 25]). When the tank motion also exhibits a rotational component (as in the experimental configurations shown in Fig. 2), dissipation may be affected, and this is taken into account by including the dependence on the ϕ parameter. Being l the distance between the centre of the tank and the fixed hinge, the amplitude of the tank vertical motion can be approximated as $a \cong l\theta$, allowing the parameter ϕ to be equivalently redefined as the ratio $\phi = (l_1\theta)/a$. As already mentioned, the article focuses mainly on assessing the sensitivity of the energy dissipated by sloshing with respect to this parameter.

Characterizing the energy dissipated by sloshing forces is important for quantifying the level of damping introduced into the response of a vibrating structure containing the tank (see Ref. [21]). This type of dissipation is generated by the phase shift between the sloshing forces and the vertical tank motion. However, energy dissipation is not the only effect given by sloshing forces. Thinking of a structure containing a tank with a liquid considered as *frozen*, the latter behaves as a ballast generating inertia affecting the dynamic response of the structure and its natural frequencies. When the fluid is considered as such, its center of mass tends to move in counter-phase with respect to the tank walls in an absolute reference system, thus generating a reduction in apparent mass (from a structural point of view). This effect results in a change in structural response frequencies that are a function of the amplitude and frequency of excitation. According to [21], the variation of the apparent mass, hereafter denoted sloshing-effective mass fraction β , can be identified by assuming the linear approximation of the sloshing force (removing the effects of the super-harmonics) and performing the ratio between the Fourier transform of the dynamic sloshing force and the related frozen liquid model force

$$\beta = \Re \left[\frac{\tilde{f}_S(\Omega)}{m_l \Omega^2 \tilde{w}(\Omega)} \right] - 1 \quad (4)$$

where $\tilde{\cdot}$ and $\Re[\cdot]$ are used, respectively, to represent the Fourier transform and the real part. This quantity represents a further signature of the vertical sloshing force that is used to compare the sloshing behaviour for different values of ϕ .

In each of the experimental configurations examined, the sloshing fluid is considered as an isolated system, similarly to what has already been proposed in Ref. [18]. Specifically, in the case study with $\phi = 0$, the sloshing fluid receives as input a motion (or acceleration) imposed to the boundary by the electrodynamic shaker and returns as output the sloshing force. This ideal condition is not perfectly reproduced also in the other two experimental configurations ($\phi = 0.26$ and $\phi = 0.52$), where tank rotation is present. In fact, the experimental system shown in Fig. 2 introduces noise due to the non-perfect rigidity of structural components (such as the rotating beam and extender). However, this noise mainly interferes at high frequencies and therefore does not significantly affect the quantification of the energy dissipated by the sloshing fluid. Thus, even in the second experimental system, the sloshing fluid can be approximately considered as an

Fig. 4 Path of the VFA harmonic tests

isolated system that returns a force and a moment as a result of the combined vertical-rotational motion imposed on the tank..

The excitation provided by the shaker is controlled in order to impose the vertical VFA harmonic acceleration law $\ddot{w} = f(t) [\cos(\int_0^t \Omega(\tau) d\tau)]$ directly to the tank, through the accelerometer placed at its position. The imposed motion law is such as to suitably cover the non-dimensional frequency $\bar{\omega}$ and amplitude \bar{a} domain of interest, following the path shown in Fig.4. The choice of this path is dictated by the need to acquire the most representative data possible to describe the dissipation induced by the sloshing fluid, in accordance with the limits of the shaker.

The dissipated work L_d is calculated based on the procedure introduced in Ref. [18], following the acquisition of the experimental acceleration and force signals relating to the VFA harmonic tests. First, a specific time instant is set representing the centre of a time interval delimited by the number of cycles selected by the user (where it is approximately guaranteed that both the frequency and amplitude of the imposed motion are constant). Within this range, the work exchanged is calculated by implementing the expression given in Eq. 1 (which is deprived of the term related to the moment in the absence of tank rotation, $\phi = 0$), averaging among the defined number of cycles. Estimation of the dissipated work throughout the domain of interest is obtained by repeating this procedure for enough time instants to cover the entire path defined by the VFA tests. Normalizing this work by the purely inertial reference contribution yields the non-dimensional dissipated energy Φ_d , which is used to present the results of the performed analyses. In particular, Fig. 5 shows this result for the purely vertical motion case ($\phi = 0$), highlighting the distribution of the non-dimensional dissipated energy Φ_d as a nonlinear function of non-dimensional frequency $\bar{\omega}$ and amplitude \bar{a} (see Ref. [18]). The distribution shows that purely vertical sloshing provides considerable dissipation over $a\Omega^2 = 1g$ of acceleration, and that the highest dissipation, corresponding to the darkest area on the map, arises close to $a\Omega^2 = 4g$ of vertical acceleration and vertical displacement about the 25% of the tank height. At high frequencies, the impact of sloshing on energy dissipation is reduced most likely due to surface tension and viscosity that may play a role in stabilizing the free surface (see Ref. [25]). Similarly, Figs. 6 and 7 show the non-dimensional dissipated energy maps obtained in the same domain for the case studies where $\phi = 0.26$ and $\phi = 0.52$, respectively. Both maps exhibit qualitatively the same distribution as the purely vertical case, with a nonlinear pattern that involves the formation of regions of maximum dissipated energy as the intensity of acceleration increases. The case with $\phi = 0$ dissipates the most energy, as illustrated also in Fig. 8, which compares the value of Φ_d at varying amplitudes \bar{a} for the fixed frequency $\bar{\omega} = 4$ (where the highest values of dissipation are reached). It is also worth rewriting the expression of non-dimensional dissipated work in order to highlight, by separating them, the contributions related to vertical motion and rotation. Specifically, Φ_d can be expressed as it follows:

$$\Phi_d = \frac{L_d}{m_1 a^2 \Omega^2} = \Phi_{d_f} + \Phi_{d_\theta} = \frac{\oint f_S dw}{m_1 a^2 \Omega^2} + \frac{\oint m_S d\theta}{m_1 a^2 \Omega^2} \quad (5)$$

where Φ_{d_f} is the non-dimensional work done by the purely vertical sloshing forces (the only contribution present in the case $\phi = 0$), whereas Φ_{d_θ} is the energy contribution related to the rotation of the tank. Defining these two contributions allows to quantify the actual contribution of the dissipated energy induced by the rotation of the tank

Fig. 5 Non-dimensional dissipated energy for the purely vertical excitation case ($\phi = 0$)

Fig. 6 Non-dimensional dissipated energy map for vertically-rotating tank ($\phi = 0.26$)

Fig. 7 Non-dimensional dissipated energy map for vertically-rotating tank ($\phi = 0.52$)

Fig. 8 Comparison of non-dimensional dissipated energy in the cases $\phi = 0, 0.26$ and 0.52 at non-dimensional frequency $\bar{\omega} = 4$

compared to that in the purely vertical case. In particular, Figs. 9 and 10 show comparisons of the energy contributions defined in Eq. 5 for the cases $\phi = 0.26$ and $\phi = 0.52$, respectively. Figure 9(a) shows how the contribution Φ_{d_θ} associated with the rotation of the tank in the case in which it is positioned at the tip of the beam ($\phi = 0.26$) is small and almost negligible compared to that associated with the purely vertical motion Φ_{d_f} shown in Fig. 9(b). In fact, the maximum value of the Φ_{d_θ} contribution is approximately 0.054. Comparison with the total dissipated energy shown in Fig. 6 proves this as well. If, on the other hand, the tank is moved to the configuration corresponding to $\phi = 0.52$, the purely rotation-related contribution becomes slightly more significant when compared to the previous case. Indeed, Fig. 10(b) shows that the Φ_{d_θ} contribution also has a well-defined region of maximum, in which the highest value of 0.16 is reached at the non-dimensional frequency $\bar{\omega} = 4$. However, its contribution to the total energy balance is not remarkable. When comparing Figs. 10(a) and 7, it can be seen that here too, the highest energy contribution always comes from the work done by the purely vertical sloshing forces. It is important to note that although the rotational contribution is not quantitatively significant, the nonlinearity of the phenomenon causes rotation to have a substantial effect on the fluid-dynamic regime of the sloshing liquid. In fact, the rotational component of the tank motion can promote fluid mixing, negating the superposition property between different contributions.

The configurations studied do not take into account any dissipative energy contributions related to lateral sloshing forces, which occur as a result of lateral tank motions. Nevertheless, the present analysis shows that dissipative effects related to the purely vertical motion of the tank are dominant. This supports the conclusion that the nonlinear sloshing reduced-order model identified in Ref. [21] with experimental data collected through tests with $\phi = 0$, can also be considered valid to a good approximation for applications in which limited tank rotations are expected (the force estimate provided by it will be slightly overestimated).

Fig. 9 Comparison of non-dimensional dissipated energy contributions for the case ($\phi = 0.26$)

Fig. 10 Comparison of non-dimensional dissipated energy contributions for the case ($\phi = 0.52$)

Implementing Eq. 4 with the experimental force data measured in the VFA tests also yields the distribution of the sloshing-effective mass fraction β in the domain of interest. In particular, Fig. 11 shows the map of $\beta(\Omega, a)$ for the purely vertical case ($\phi = 0$) which results to be negative throughout the frequency-amplitude domain. Therefore, the relative motion of fluid center of mass is always counter-phased with respect to the tank (see Ref. [21]). Similarly, Fig. 12 shows the experimentally characterised beta distribution in the case $\phi = 0.26$. It is perfectly consistent with that obtained in the absence of tank rotation, also in terms of the (negative) values obtained when varying the amplitude and frequency of the imposed excitation. In the case $\phi = 0.52$, on the other hand, the higher weight of the rotational contribution of the tank motion has an influence on the values of the beta parameter, which are lower (in absolute value). However, the distribution in the domain remains almost similar, retaining the presence of an increasingly darker region (where the effective mass fraction is larger in absolute value) accordingly to the intensity $a\Omega^2$ of the imposed acceleration.

Fig. 11 Sloshing-effective mass fraction map for purely vertical sloshing ($\phi = 0$)

Fig. 12 Slushing-effective mass fraction map for vertically-rotating tank ($\phi = 0.26$)

Fig. 13 Slushing-effective mass fraction map for vertically-rotating tank ($\phi = 0.52$)

IV. Concluding remarks

In this paper, an experimental study was conducted in order to evaluate the combined effects of rotation and vertical tank motion on the dissipative behaviour of slushing. For this purpose, two different experimental configurations were considered. The first, mounts a box-shaped tank half-filled with water directly on an electrodynamic shaker capable of imposing vertical seismic vibrations. Using acceleration sensors and load cells, it was possible to measure the motion of the tank and the slushing force exerted by the liquid on the tank walls. This set-up allows the vertical component of the tank motion to be isolated, generating a purely vertical slushing problem. The second experimental set-up, on the other hand, was designed to ensure simultaneous vertical and rotational excitation of the tank using the same shaker and box-shaped tank. Specifically, the set-up allowed the tank to be mounted on a rigid hinged beam set into rotation by the vertical vibrations imposed by the shaker extender to which it is connected (via a hinge). Similarly, this system was also equipped with the appropriate sensors to evaluate the vertical acceleration and rotation of the tank, as well as the force

and sloshing moment.

A sensitivity analysis was carried out by quantifying the energy dissipated by sloshing as the degree of combination between vertical and rotational motion of the tank varies. The degree of combination was varied by placing the tank in different positions on the beam, emphasizing more or less the rotational contribution than the vertical one. Two different tank positions on the rotating beam were considered, resulting in two case studies. Comparison with the dissipation induced by purely vertical sloshing in the first experimental setup revealed the extent to which tank rotation in the two cases mentioned above affects the total energy balance. The data used in the energy characterization were obtained by performing harmonic excitation tests at variable frequency and amplitude, covering a domain of interest based on the shaker capabilities.

Comparison between nonlinear distributions of energy dissipated by sloshing in the different case studies showed that the energy contribution strictly related to tank rotation is almost negligible compared with that induced by purely vertical motion. In addition, purely vertical sloshing provides slightly larger dissipation overall than that measured in cases where tank rotation is involved. However, there is almost the same dependence on the amplitude and frequency of excitation, which results in obtaining consistent energy maps with the purely vertical one. Similar considerations apply to the sloshing effective mass fraction, which is included in the sensitivity analysis performed in this paper. Thus, the nonlinear reduced-order models identified in previous work based on experimental data collected in purely vertical sloshing tests can also be used with good reliability in applications where small tank rotations are expected (unless a slight overestimation of the overall dissipated energy).

The present work does not take into account the effects related to lateral sloshing forces that arise as a result of the combined motion of the tank. This sets the stage for future developments involving other degrees of freedom of the tank in order to obtain a more complete experimental characterization of sloshing dissipative behavior. As a result, new reduced-order models that are even more representative of the phenomenon will be identified using more comprehensive experimental data.

Acknowledgements

This paper has been supported by SLOWD project. The SLOWD project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 815044.

References

- [1] Gambioli, F., Chamos, A., Jones, S., Guthrie, P., Webb, J., Levenhagen, J., Behruzi, P., Mastroddi, F., Malan, A., Longshaw, S., Cooper, J., Gonzalez, L., and Marrone, S., "Sloshing Wing Dynamics -Project Overview Sloshing Wing Dynamics – Project Overview," *Proceedings of 8th Transport Research Arena TRA*, 2020.
- [2] Graham, E., and Rodriguez, A. M., "The Characteristics of Fuel Motion which Affect Airplane Dynamics," Tech. rep., Douglas Aircraft Co. inc., Defense Technical Information Center, 1951.
- [3] Abramson, H. N., "The dynamic behaviour of liquids in moving containers with applications to space vehicle technology," *Natl. Aeronaut. Sp. Adm.*, 1966, p. 464.
- [4] Ibrahim, R. A., "Assessment of breaking waves and liquid sloshing impact," *Nonlinear Dynamics*, Vol. 100, No. 3, 2020, pp. 1837–1925.
- [5] Saltari, F., Traini, A., Gambioli, F., and Mastroddi, F., "A linearized reduced-order model approach for sloshing to be used for aerospace design," *Aerospace Science and Technology*, Vol. 108, 2021, p. 106369.
- [6] Firouz-Abadi, R. D., Zarifian, P., and Haddadpour, H., "Effect of Fuel Sloshing in the External Tank on the Flutter of Subsonic Wings," *Journal of Aerospace Engineering*, Vol. 27, No. 5, 2014, p. 04014021.
- [7] Farhat, C., Chiu, E. K.-y., Amsallem, D., Schotté, J.-S., and Ohayon, R., "Modeling of Fuel Sloshing and its Physical Effects on Flutter," *AIAA Journal*, Vol. 51, No. 9, 2013, pp. 2252–2265.
- [8] Pizzoli, M., "Investigation of Sloshing Effects on Flexible Aircraft Stability and Response," *Aerotecnica Missili e Spazio*, Vol. 99, 2020, p. 297–308.
- [9] Benjamin, T. B., Ursell, F. J., and Taylor, G. I., "The stability of the plane free surface of a liquid in vertical periodic motion," *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London. Series A. Mathematical and Physical Sciences*, Vol. 225, No. 1163, 1954, pp. 505–515.

- [10] Douady, S., “Experimental study of the Faraday instability,” *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, Vol. 221, 1990, p. 383–409.
- [11] Bredmose, H., Brocchini, M., Peregrine, D. H., and Thais, L., “Experimental investigation and numerical modelling of steep forced water waves,” *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, Vol. 490, 2003, p. 217–249.
- [12] Lewis, D. J., and A. P. R. S. L., “The instability of liquid surfaces when accelerated in a direction perpendicular to their planes. II,” *Proc. R. Soc. London. Ser. A. Math. Phys. Sci.*, Vol. 202, No. 1068, 1950, pp. 81–96.
- [13] Gambioli, F., Usach, R. A., Wilson, T., and Behruzi, P., “Experimental Evaluation of Fuel Sloshing Effects on wing dynamics,” *18th Int. Forum Aeroelasticity Struct. Dyn. IFASD 2019*, 2019.
- [14] Titurus, B., Cooper, J. E., Saltari, F., Mastroddi, F., and Gambioli, F., “Analysis of a Sloshing Beam Experiment,” *International Forum on Aeroelasticity and Structural Dynamics. Savannah, Georgia, USA*, Vol. 139, 2019.
- [15] Martínez-Carrascal, J., and González-Gutiérrez, L., “Experimental study of the liquid damping effects on a SDOF vertical sloshing tank,” *Journal of Fluids and Structures*, Vol. 100, 2021, p. 103172.
- [16] Coppotelli, G., Franceschini, G., Titurus, B., and Cooper, J. E., “Oma Experimental Identification of the Damping Properties of a Sloshing System,” *Proceedings of Conference on Noise and Vibration ISMA 2020*, Vol. Virtual Event Paper, september 2020.
- [17] Coppotelli, G., Franceschini, G., Mastroddi, F., and Saltari, F., “Experimental Investigation on the damping mechanism in sloshing structures,” *AIAA Scitech Forum*, 2021.
- [18] Saltari, F., Pizzoli, M., Coppotelli, G., Gambioli, F., Cooper, J. E., and Mastroddi, F., “Experimental characterisation of sloshing tank dissipative behaviour in vertical harmonic excitation,” *Journal of fluids and structures*, Vol. 109, 2022, p. 103478.
- [19] Menon, K., and Mittal, R., “Aeroelastic response of an airfoil to gusts: Prediction and control strategies from computed energy maps,” *Journal of Fluids and Structures*, Vol. 97, 2020, p. 103078.
- [20] Saltari, F., Pizzoli, M., Mastroddi, F., Gambioli, F., and Jetzschmann, C., “Nonlinear sloshing integrated aeroelastic analyses of a research wing prototype,” *AIAA Science and Technology Forum and Exposition, AIAA SciTech Forum 2022*, 2022.
- [21] Saltari, F., Pizzoli, M., Gambioli, F., Jetzschmann, C., and Mastroddi, F., “Sloshing reduced-order model based on neural networks for aeroelastic analyses,” *Aerospace Science and Technology*, 2022, p. 107708.
- [22] Pagliaroli, T., Gambioli, F., Saltari, F., and Cooper, J., “Proper orthogonal decomposition, dynamic mode decomposition, wavelet and cross wavelet analysis of a sloshing flow,” *Journal of Fluids and Structures*, Vol. 112, 2022.
- [23] Calderon-Sanchez, J., Martínez-Carrascal, J., Gonzalez-Gutierrez, L. M., and Colagrossi, A., “A global analysis of a coupled violent vertical sloshing problem using an SPH methodology,” *Engineering Applications of Computational Fluid Mechanics*, Vol. 15, No. 1, 2021, pp. 865–888.
- [24] Martínez-Carrascal, J., and González-Gutiérrez, L., “Experimental study of the liquid damping effects on a SDOF vertical sloshing tank,” *Journal of Fluids and Structures - Submitted*, 2020.
- [25] Constantin, L., De Courcy, J., Titurus, B., Rendall, T., and Cooper, J., “Analysis of damping from vertical sloshing in a SDOF system,” *Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing*, Vol. 152, 2021, p. 107452.